

INTEGRATION OF SOCIAL-INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the integration of social and informational competence of students of higher educational institutions based on interactive educational methods and innovative approaches based on their capabilities.*

Keywords: *social-informational competence, electronic educational resource, interactive educational method, pedagogical software tool, interactive story, competence, working with information.*

It is necessary to clarify the concept of "social-informational competence" and its components in relation to the information and culture of a specific socialization process. In solving the main problem of this research, it is necessary to consider such a component of "social-informational competence" as culture.

Researchers say that the concept of culture is a complex that includes knowledge, faith, art, spirituality, law, customs, and all other skills and habits that a person acquires as a member of society, or is understood in a broad ethnographic context.

Further clarification and wider study of this concept is reflected in the works of modern German researchers in the field of intercultural communication. In these works, the authors define culture, on the one hand, as a set of subjective values, norms, ideas, worldview, and on the other hand, as a set of objectives - activities, behavior methods, working with information.

Didactic requirements, methodical and technical requirements for creating electronic educational resources were studied in the module of requirements for the creation of electronic educational resources.

In the second module, the contents of the structural components of the electronic educational resources, the regulatory documents component, the content determining component, the methodical component, and the evaluation components were delivered to the future engineer-pedagogues through educational methods.

In the technology module of creation of electronic educational resources, the stages of creation were carried out using pedagogical software tools.

In the fourth module, the implementation of the electronic educational resource, its use, and the evaluation of the knowledge of future engineer-pedagogues were carried out.

Lessons were conducted with extensive use of interactive educational methods such as Briefing, SMART, Staircase, Web-quest. These educational methods are creative educational methods designed for teaching subjects related to information and communication technologies. The educational process is based on the use of electronic educational resources in lectures, pedagogical software tools (Mentimeter, Padlet, Kahoot!, Wooflash, Socrative, Quizlet), programming languages, and educational platforms in practical and laboratory sessions. Information systems (Hemis, Moodle), e-mail, chat, chat-forum, ISQ, IP-telephony, blogs, video

blog, live magazines, wikipedia, interPedagogika iv media technology, online video conferencing tools and technologies. widely used.

We will try to briefly describe below the interactive educational methods and their capabilities that were used in pedagogical experiments during our research work and ensured the achievement of efficiency.

"Briefing" educational method. "Briefing" can be described as a short press conference devoted to the discussion of an issue or question related to a process or event. The stages of carrying out this method in the educational process are as follows: 1. Presentation part. 2. Discussion process (based on questions and answers). The briefing method can be used in the analysis of training results. Also, as a certain form of practical games, it will be possible to organize briefings with the participants dedicated to the discussion of a current topic or problem. It can also be used to present mobile applications created by students or trainees.

SMART method. One of the most effective methods for determining goals is the SMART method. SMART is an abbreviation of the English word capital letters. Thus, SMART: Specific – a specific goal; Measurable - measure; Achievable – how; Realistic - actuality; Timed is a specified time. Let's take a closer look at each component.

SMART is a method of a modern approach to setting goals and defining tasks. allows to present.

The SMART method is an interactive educational method that allows you to model situations in the organization of the educational process in online and offline modes based on modern information and communication technologies and tools. It ensures the implementation of the principle of the lesson process in a convenient place and at a convenient time. This method is implemented using mobile platforms, internet system services, teleconference communication, webinars, blogs, video and audio media.

It ensures the rapid distribution of information and the use of information on social media in the educational process. Provides up-to-date and complete information on the subject being studied. Allows you to organize online consultations with expert practitioners. Students communicate with each other on the topic being studied, and the material solved by the student can be used to teach the next audience.

Figure 1. General scheme of the SMART method

S-specific goal– improvement of the education system.

M-measurulle– the readiness of the student to perform his professional tasks, laws, concepts of modernization of education specified in the qualification requirements of the educational field.

A-ashieweble– Development of characteristics, type and form of education, training period, admission procedure, contingent and training expenses of specialists in the fields of professional activity.

R-relevant– Training of competitive highly qualified personnel according to international standards, based on the requirements of the labor market.

T- time-baund– 2021-2023 academic years.

"Step-by-step" method. This technology is conducted in writing and presented with students individually or in groups. This technology can be used in all classes. Training based on these technologies will be conducted in the following order:

1. The members of the small group are introduced to the purpose of the exercise and the procedure for conducting it, they are distributed sheets with a small topic (or some type of tasks of different complexity levels) written on the left side of the paper.

2. The teacher assigns the members of the small group to familiarize themselves with the sub-topics written in the handout and write down what they know on the blank space of the paper together with their team and sets a time.

3. After the handouts are filled, one of the group members will make a presentation. During the presentation, the material prepared by the groups is logically hung on the board of the audience (in the form of a ladder).

4. The teacher comments on the materials prepared by the groups, evaluates them and concludes the lesson. such an organization of the educational session teaches students to think independently, to remember the subjects learned and learned, to express them in writing, to summarize thoughts.

Webquest – this is a modern educational technology that includes targeted search activities of students using Internet information resources to complete a specific educational task.

Creation of a database on the problem, all its sections are prepared by students. Writing an interactive story (students can choose options to continue the work; for this, two or three possible directions are shown each time;). The challenge is to create a paper that provides an analysis of the problem and invites students to agree or disagree with the authors. Answers and questions are developed by students who have studied this person in depth.

The application of the Web-quest educational method to the educational process provides the following opportunities: - to increase the motivation for self-study; formation of new competencies; development of creative potential; increase personal self-esteem; - development of personal qualities not required during the educational process, creative abilities, etc.

Web-quest is a group activity that includes effective interaction of all participants to achieve a common goal, to create a common end product of research.

The motivational moment of the quest is the distribution of roles among the participants, each of them performs a certain function, is responsible for a certain type of activity; The web-quest can be created both within one discipline and interdisciplinary, in which the basic knowledge of future engineer-pedagogues of different disciplines can be used.

The use of the Web-quest educational method serves to develop the following competencies in future engineer-pedagogues:

Information: work with information, analyze, generalize, connect with previously learned, draw conclusions.

Projecting: developing ideas, finding ways to solve problems, predicting the possible consequences of decisions.

Communicative: to enter into dialogue, to defend one's point of view.

Interactive: it serves to develop the skills of cooperating with others, accepting their point of view, trusting partners, being responsible for the result of one's work, working with media and computer tools.

Electronic educational methodological complexes (EEMC) – It is a collection of resources that provide the opportunity to receive education in the online system.

This type of educational resources includes the working curriculum of the educational module, the text of lectures, the description of seminars and practical exercises, the topics of abstracts, tests and controls, the educational module for future engineer-pedagogues includes materials such as methodological recommendations for effective learning, a list of literature that allows independent learning of the basics of the educational module.

In conclusion, it can be said that the principles of working with information serve as a theoretical basis for the integration of national culture. The methodological basis is a set of conceptual guidelines for the implementation of these principles. Technological support is a system of educational goals and means of achieving them.

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